

**Consumption efficiency of leaf extracts of piper methysticum g. Forst against larvae of
plutella xylostella l. (Lepidoptera: Plutellidae)**

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ABSTRACT

Diversity of plant species is a source of bio-chemicals. *Piper methysticum* plant is typical of Papua Indonesia used by society of Marid Merauke Papua as herbal medicine and traditional drinks in daily life. *P. methysticum* has potential as drugs, herbicides and fungicides. This research was conducted to investigate the influence of *P. methysticum* extract on ingesting activity and consumption efficiency against the 3rd instar larvae of *P. xylostella*. Antifeedant and consumption efficiency test were done by using no choice method. Cabbage leaf (4 x 4 cm) was dipped into n-hexane, ethyl acetate, diethyl ether, and n-butanol with the concentrations equal to LC₁₅, LC₂₅, LC₅₀, and LC₇₅. The results showed that the extract of ethyl acetate of *P. methysticum* leaf was able to suppress ingesting activity of larva *P. xylostella* instar III as much as 92.79%. *P. methysticum* extract was proven not efficient and effective to be feed for larva *P. xylostella* instar III. It reduced relative consumption rate, relative growth rate, efficiency of conversion of digested food, efficiency of conversion of ingested food, and it increased average digested food. Extract of *P. methysticum* is potentially developed as botanical insecticide to control pests *P. xylostella*.

Keywords: *P. methysticum*, *P. xylostella*, antifeedant, consumption efficiency.

INTRODUCTION

Kava (*Piper methysticum*) is one species of plants that has been used as traditional medicine and cultivated by the Marind tribe in the lowlands of Merauke, Papua. This plant is widely used by Marind people for medicinal, social and cultural purposes. *P. methysticum* contains chemical compounds alkaloids (piperidine, pipermethysticine), flavonoids, resins (kava lactone), kawain, tannins, saponins, anthraquinones, and a few essential oils (Salim et al., (2004). These plants are effective as antifungal, antibiotics, antiseptic, antimicrobial and narcotic as well as effective for controlling fungal *Alternaria solani* Ell. & Mart. (Pleosporaceae), *Botrytis cinerea* (De Bary) Whetzel. (Sclerotiniaceae), *Ceratocystis*

ulmi Buism. *Sclerotinia fructicola* G.Winter. (Sclerotiniaceae) (Grainge and Ahmed, 1988). Since the 20th century, kava has become popular in the Western world as an herbal supplement for anxiety and insomnia (Rowe et al., 2011).

Symptoms of *P. xylostella* resistance to insecticides have occurred against 46 insecticidal formulations of the organophosphate, carbamate, pyrethroid and organochlorine groups (Sun, 1992). Shelton et al. (1993). Goudgnom et al. (2000) and Zao et al. (2002) reported that *P. xylostella* had resistance to insecticides of metomyl active ingredients, permethrin, metamidofos, deltamethrin and spinosad. The results of research on *P. xylostella* cabbage caterpillar in various production centers in Central Java and Yogyakarta have experienced resistance to insecticides of deltamethrin active ingredients (Listyaningrum, 2003; and Rahman, 2004). while Udiarto and Setiawati (2007) reported *P. xylostella* in Canning area has been resistant to fipronil, abamectin and *B. Thuringiensis* insecticides, resistant to abamectin in Garut area, and resistant to fipronil in Lembang area. Canning and Buleleng, *P. xylostella* pest control is largely dependent on the use of chemical insecticides. Unwise use of insecticides causes environmental problems, beneficial non-targeted insecticide poisoning and resistance to chemical insecticides (Abo-Elghar et al., 2005).

The diamondback moth, *P. xylostella* (L.) is one of the most destructive insect pests of cruciferous vegetables. farmers very often resort to spraying chemical insecticides at high dosages with frequent applications. The intensive and continuous use of insecticides can cause insect pest resistance. *P. xylostella* has developed resistance in recent years to some of the conventional insecticides.

Worries about the danger of chemical insecticide triggers researchers to find an alternative eco-friendly method in controlling insect pests. One of the promising alternative methods is using herbal plants that contain bioactive chemical compound (Vanichpakorn et al., 2010). Moreover, they are useful in integrated pest control management (Schmutterer, 1992). Herbal plants are mostly used in controlling insect pests. It is also known because of a strong correlation between herbal plants and pesticide (Yang and Tang, 1988). Bioactive compound of plants comes from metabolic result of secondary plants.

Secondary metabolic compound is commonly known to have bioactivity capability that could protect plants from pest attack and its environment. This secondary compound could be potential in helping plants to survive and to control insect pest; it serves as toxin, antifeedant, growth inhibitor, attractant, repellent, and protectant from any disorder coming from reproductive behaviour (Remoser and Stoffolano, 1994; Sumarsono, 1996). The deleterious effects of plant extracts or pure compounds on insects can be manifested in several manners including toxicity, mortality, antifeedant growth inhibitor.

suppression of reproductive behaviour and reduction of fecundity and fertility. antifecundancy. growth inhibition. perturbation of reproductive behaviour (reduction of fecundity and fertility) (Rachid et al., 2006). Secondary metabolic compound which has bioactive potential in protecting plant can be used as a source of ingredients for insecticide to control pests. Plants with intensive insecticide were collected and identified. The plants considered promising in this research comprised those of family of Meliaceae. Rutaceae. Annonaceae. Asteraceae. Piperaceae. and Labiatae (Isman, 1995; Jacobson, 1989; Schmutterer, 1992).

The biological activity of secondary metabolic compound in plants has been investigated continuously. One of plant sources which is potentially developed as the source of insecticide is *P. methysticum* (Piperaceae). This is the native plant of Papua Indonesian taken from Merauke Regency. and is commonly used by local tribe of Marid Merauke of Papua Indonesian as herbal medicine and traditional drink. *P. methysticum* contains chemical compound such as kavain. dihydrokavain. and dihydromethysticin. which are narcotic and sedative (Agusta et al., 1997). Another research revealed that such kind of plant contains chemical compounds such as alkaloid (piperidine. pipermethysticine). flavonoid. resin (kava lactone). kavain. tannin. saponin. anthraquinone. and a little essential oil (Salim et al., 2004; Lestari et al., 2015). The identification results by Lopez and Yefchak (2009). kava extract *Piper methysticum* contained compound of 7. 8 Dihydrokavain. Kavain. 5. 6-Dehydrokavain. 5. 6. 7. 8-Tetrahydroyangonin. 7. 8-Dihydromethysticin. Yangonin. Methysticin. Bornyl cinnamate. Dihydroxy-methoxyphenylphenyl-propen-one. Hydroxy-dimethoxyphenyl-3-phenyl-2-propen-1-one^d. Hydroxy-dimethoxyphenyl-3-methoxyphenyl-2-propen-1-one^e. The six major kavalactones are quantified by HPLC and used for the chemotype identification. The chemotype is most importance for assessment of kava quality standards (Lebot and Levesque. Lebot et al., 1997; Lebot and Simeoni, 2004; Lebot, 2006; Teschke et al., 2009; 2011; Showman et al., 2015). This plant is also considered effectively as antifungal. antibiotic. antiseptic. antimicrobial. and is also effective in controlling fungus *Alternaria solani* EII. & Mart. (Pleosporaceae). *Botrytis cinerea* (De Bary) Whetzel. (Sclerotiniaceae). *Ceratocystis ulmi* Buism. *Sclerotinia fructicola* G. Winter. (Sclerotiniaceae) (Grainge and Ahmed, 1988). It was also found that the root of *P. methysticum* is potential as herbicide and fungicide (Xuan et al., 2003a; 2003b).

The antifecundant effect of plant extracts has been studied by many authors (Roman, 2010; Alagarmalai, 2012; Jeyasankar et al., 2014; Summarwar and Pandey, 2015). However. the effects of *P. methysticum* on acute or chronic toxicity have not been widely reported. According to Grainge and Ahmed

(1988). *P. methysticum* contains alkaloid compound which inhibits the growth of insects. Regarding to such information, this experiment is aimed to test *P. methysticum* leaf extract at sublethal concentration by observing ingesting efficiency. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the effect of *P. methysticum* leaf extract on ingesting activity efficiency consumption in the use of food for against instar larvae of *P. xylostella*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection and Extraction of Plant Material

Plant species were collected from around Sota District, Merauke, Papua. Identified plant species was done in the Faculty of Biology of Cenderawasih University of Papua.

The plant materials were thoroughly washed with tap water and shade dried under room temperature ($30^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 6^{\circ}\text{C}$) At the Basic Laboratory of Assessment Institute for Agricultural Technology (AIAT) Papua. After complete drying the plant materials were powdered using electric blender and sieved a size of 50 mesh. 1000 g of plant powder was extracted with methanol, diethyl ether, ethyl acetate and n-butanol, sequentially with increasing polarity of solvents and filtered through Whatman's No. 1 filter paper. The solvents from the crude extract were evaporated to air dryness at room temperature. The crude extracts were collected in clean borosyl vials and stored in the refrigerator at 4°C for sub-sequent bioassay against *P. xylostella*.

Antifeedant Test

Antifeedant test was done to observe the existence of compounds in the plant extract that function as antifeedant, by applying no choice method or no selection method using cabbage leaf (4x4 cm). The experiment was performed using complete randomized design (CRD), four concentrations of *P. methysticum* leaf extract, and four replications. The extract concentration tested was obtained from Probit analysis which was equal to LC_{15} ; LC_{25} ; LC_{50} ; LC_{75} ; and control (0%). Each concentration level consisted of 10 third instar larvae of *P. xylostella*. Each larvae was laid individually on 9x9 cm petri dish.

Getting the initial wet weight of leaves was prepared by dipping into each concentration tested and dried oven. The dried leaves was placed on filter paper laid on the petri dish size 9 cm containing 10 3rd instar initial weight of each larvae *P. xylostella*. The observation was conducted every 24 hours and ended when the larvae reached the last instar stage, the larvae stopped ingesting. Antifeedant with non-choice method was calculated according to the following formula (Hassanali and Bentley, 1987):

$$AFI = (K-P/K+P) \times 100 \% \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

AFI = Antifeeding index; K= the weight of control leaf consumed; P= the weight of treated leaf consumed.

To categorize the antifeedant criteria of using plants Liu *et al.*, (2007) formula : AFI < 20% = no antifeeding activity (-); 20% > AFI ≥ 20% = slightly antifeeding activity (+); 50% > AFI ≥ 50% = medium antifeeding activity (++); AFI ≥ 70% = strong antifeeding activity (+++)

Measurement on Efficiency of Feed for Larva Instar III *P. xylostella*

The test was initially started by preparing pesticide-free cabbage leaf for 3rd instar larvae *P. xylostella* with 4 types of concentration level including control. The concentration used was equal to LC₁₅; LC₂₅; LC₅₀; LC₇₅; and control (0%). Each concentration consisted of 10 3rd instar larvae which just shed their skin and have not consume the leaves yet.

Firstly, *P. xylostella* larvae and cabbage leaves were weighed to obtain the initial wet weight. The each larvae were laid individually on 9 cm petri dish to avoid cannibalism. filled feed which contained extract of certain concentration. The observation was done every 24 hours and the treatment was ceased when the larvae reached the last 4th instar. Larvae, remaining feed, and stool of each vial were weighed and dried in oven with the temperature of 60°C until they reached constant dry weight. The response of the 4th instar *P. xylostella* larvae to *P. methysticum* extract related with their feed were calculated using the larvae gravimetry with the following formula Waldbauer (1968):

$$\text{Growth Rate/GR} = G/T \text{ (mg/day)} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

$$\text{Relative Growth Rate/RGR} = G/TA \text{ (mg/mg/day)} \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

$$\text{Consumption Rate/CR} = E/T \text{ (mg/day)} \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

$$\text{Relative consumption Rate/RCR} = E/TA \text{ (mg/mg/day)} \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

$$\text{Efficiency of Conversion of Digested Food/ECD} = G/ (E-F) \times 100\% \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

$$\text{Efficiency of Conversion of Ingested Food/ECI} = G/E \times 100\% \dots\dots\dots (7)$$

$$\text{Approximate Digestibility/AD} = (E-F)/E \times 100\% \dots\dots\dots (8)$$

Where:

G = increasing weight of larvae during ingesting period (the last dry weight of larvae is subtracted by the initial dry weight of larvae)

- F = the amount of feed ingested (the initial dry weight of feed subtracted by the last dry weight of feed).
 F = the dry weight of stool
 T = the time taken for ingestion
 A = Average weight of larvae during treatment (initial dry weight of larvae plus last dry weight of larvae. then divided by two)

Statistic Analysis

The calculation was based on dry weight condition. the dry weight of ingested leaves. the weight of larvae. and the weight of the stool of larvae used to sum up ingesting activity and efficiency of consumption arranged in Completely Randomised Design (CRD) and data analysed by using variance. followed by multiple range test of Duncan at 5% significance (Steel and Torrie, 1993) and SAS program (SAS Institute, 1990).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Antifeedant Test

P. methycticum extracts coming from various concentrations were significantly influential in ingesting activity of larvae instar II of *P. xylostella* (Table 1). The treatment given to *P. methycticum* extract of different concentrations in between concentrations tested could hamper ingesting activities as much as 9.42 – 92.79%. These figures were significantly different from those of control, implying that the higher the concentration was, the more significantly the ingesting activity was inhibited.

P. methycticum extract of fractions such as n-hexane, ethyl acetate, diethyl ether, and n-butanol affected anti-ingesting activity of larvae *P. xylostella*. The experiment revealed that at the concentration equal to LC₁₅ – LC₇₅, the weight of leaves (22.38-52.42 mg) consumed by tested larvae showed significant difference compared to those of control. The weight of leaf consumed of different extract was 1.90-18.08 mg; 1.32-28.82 mg, 2.65-18.64 mg, and 3.33-41.42 mg. The decreasing amount of feed consumed by larvae *P. xylostella* was caused by the existence of allelochemical compound in *P. methycticum* extract which is toxic. The decrease occurred because the larvae neutralised the existing toxin. Some energy which was supposed to be used for growth was used to neutralise the toxin (Sahayaraj et al., 2008).

Table 1. The effect of extracts *P. methyticum* on feeding intensity (consumed leaf weight- mg) and Inhibition weight of *P. xylostella* larvae to non-choice test

Crude Ekstrak	Concentrate(ppm)	Consumed leaf weight (mg)	AFI (%)
n-Hexane	0	22.38 ± 3.49 c	-
	LC ₁₅	18.08 ± 4.82 b	11.69 ± 9.79 a
	LC ₂₅	14.97 ± 2.42 b	19.85 ± 9.17 a
	LC ₅₀	3.07 ± 1.45 a	76.12 ± 10.22 b
	LC ₇₅	1.90 ± 0.66 a	84.54 ± 4.43 b
Ethyl acetate	0	33.85 ± 5.18 e	-
	LC ₁₅	28.82 ± 2.31 d	9.42 ± 4.40 a
	LC ₂₅	22.65 ± 4.05 c	19.97 ± 4.67 b
	LC ₅₀	7.60 ± 1.31 b	64.23 ± 5.15 c
	LC ₇₅	1.32 ± 0.26 a	92.79 ± 1.79 d
Diethyl ether	0	25.03 ± 2.35 d	-
	LC ₁₅	18.64 ± 1.88 c	13.43 ± 6.09 a
	LC ₂₅	11.25 ± 2.05 b	38.04 ± 10.17 b
	LC ₅₀	4.84 ± 1.57 a	68.06 ± 8.28 c
	LC ₇₅	2.65 ± 0.20 a	80.21 ± 2.25 d
n-Butanol	0	52.42 ± 6.42 d	-
	LC ₁₅	41.08 ± 2.84 c	11.81 ± 8.46 a
	LC ₂₅	14.12 ± 1.59 b	57.39 ± 4.26 b
	LC ₅₀	6.01 ± 0.98 a	79.74 ± 2.76 c
	LC ₇₅	3.33 ± 0.08 a	87.76 ± 1.49 c

The results are Means±SD; Within the column similar alphabets are statistically not significant (p > 0.05 by DMRT).

The biggest eating inhibition was shown at the concentration equal to LC₇₅ as much as 92.79% from the ethyl acetate extract, 87.76% from butanol extract, 84.54% from n-hexane extract, and 80.21% from diethyl ether extract. The higher the concentration was, the stronger the effect of eating inhibition would be. Such an inhibition could occur just because there were active chemical compounds found in each extract tested. Some of the chemical compounds gave taste larvae would not like; they worked by attacking the nerves of the larvae, so the larvae would lose their appetite to eat more, even lose it completely. Some researchers suggested that a compound which could functioned as antifeedant was seen to be influential in the concentration, which could inhibit eating activity up to 50% (Bernays and Chapman, 1994).

The larvae stopped eating simply because of the alkaloid, terpenoid, and tannin content found in the *P. methyticum* extract. The phytochemical analysis results of *P. methyticum* extract (Lestari *et al.*, 2015) showed that the extract of *P. methyticum* leaf positively contained alkaloid, flavonoid, tannin, and saponin. Allelochemical compound working as antifeedant is generally in the form of alkaloid and terpenoid (Schoonhoven, 1982).

Based on the criteria antifeedant according to Liu *et al.*, 2007, *P. metyticum* extract of some solvents have antifeedant properties ranging concentration L₂₅-L₇₅ classified slightly antifeeding activity (+) to strong antifeeding activity (+++). This suggests that *P. metyticum* extract can be used as an antifeedant for the larvae *P. xylostella*.

It is commonly known that nature has its plants rich with chemical compounds such as phenol, alkaloid, flavonoid, terpene, quinone, coumarin, and many others with their defensive capability towards insects. Those chemical compounds have their biological activities such as antifeedant, oviposition deterrent, insecticide, ovicidal, and IGRs. Identifying the sources of chemical compounds related with useful biological activities of pest is a starting point needed in the development of botanical products (Isman, 1997). Antifeedant is defined as chemical compound which could hamper eating activity without directly killing insects; the insects stay in their leafy habitats until they are dead due to being hungry. The antifeedant considered powerful may involve quinolone, alkaloid indole, lactone, sesquiterpene, diterpinoids, and triterpinoids (Krishnappa et al., 2010).

Consumption Efficiency

Growth and Development are two of some elements in forms of life. Insects will give response to those elements in two ways. Firstly, insects may select their feed to balance the feed intake (Ahmad et al., 1993; Ahmad et al, 2001). Secondly, insects may manage the proportion of feed ingested (Scriber and Slansky 1981).

The response of insects to allelochemical compound in the feed consumed could reduce the rate of consumption. It could also affect efficiency of consumption such as relative consumption rate, the amount of feed digested, efficiency conversion of feed ingested, and relative growth rate, which could eventually reduce the life span of insects (Simpson and Simpson, 1990).

Table 2 and 3 present the research results of *P. methyticum* extract effect on the efficiency of feed for larvae instar III *P. xylostella* which comprises relative consumption rate (RCR), relative growth rate (RGR), efficiency conversion of digested food (ECD), efficiency conversion of ingested food (ECI), and average digested food (AD).

Table 2. Effect of extract of leaves of *P. methysticum* against Relative Consumption Rate (RCR) and Relative Growth Rate (RGR) third instar larvae of *P. xylostella*.

Crude Ekstrak Concentrate (ppm)	CR (mg/day)	RCR (mg/mg/day)	GR (mg/day)	RGR (mg/mg/day)
n-Hexane				
0	2.27 ± 1.04 b	5.02 ± 1.73 b	0.26 ± 0.17 b	0.55 ± 0.15 c
LC ₁₅	2.24 ± 0.80 b	4.48 ± 1.03 b	0.24 ± 0.11 b	0.26 ± 0.13 b
LC ₂₅	0.96 ± 0.33 a	2.50 ± 1.13 a	0.12 ± 0.05 a	0.29 ± 0.04 b
LC ₅₀	0.90 ± 0.36 a	3.29 ± 0.60 a	0.08 ± 0.03 a	0.21 ± 0.04 b
LC ₇₅	0.84 ± 0.39 a	3.18 ± 1.12 a	0.06 ± 0.04 a	0.06 ± 0.03 a
Ethyl acetate 0				
LC ₁₅	5.03 ± 0.87 d	3.72 ± 0.10 c	0.78 ± 0.16 b	0.73 ± 0.18 c
LC ₂₅	3.20 ± 0.51 c	3.13 ± 0.52 bc	0.60 ± 0.13 b	0.58 ± 0.09 b
LC ₅₀	2.10 ± 0.69 b	3.07 ± 0.58 bc	0.27 ± 0.12 a	0.47 ± 0.09 b
LC ₇₅	1.04 ± 0.40 a	2.56 ± 0.76 b	0.22 ± 0.11 a	0.31 ± 0.06 a
	1.08 ± 0.26 a	1.73 ± 0.42 a	0.16 ± 0.07 a	0.21 ± 0.06 a
Diethyl ether 0				
LC ₁₅	1.65 ± 0.35 a	0.88 ± 0.29 b	0.29 ± 0.09 d	0.16 ± 0.05 d
LC ₂₅	1.49 ± 0.49 a	0.86 ± 0.11 a	0.21 ± 0.08 c	0.10 ± 0.03 c
LC ₅₀	1.57 ± 0.59 a	0.84 ± 0.15 a	0.17 ± 0.04 c	0.09 ± 0.02 c
LC ₇₅	1.42 ± 0.31 a	0.84 ± 0.26 a	0.09 ± 0.04 b	0.05 ± 0.02 b
	1.31 ± 0.16 a	0.71 ± 0.13 a	0.02 ± 0.003 a	0.01 ± 0.002 a
n-Butanol				
0	2.45 ± 0.59 d	1.28 ± 0.25 b	0.48 ± 0.20 b	0.25 ± 0.08 c
LC ₁₅	2.34 ± 0.36 cd	0.97 ± 0.41 a	0.48 ± 0.20 b	0.17 ± 0.04 b
LC ₂₅	1.88 ± 0.60 bc	0.86 ± 0.12 a	0.31 ± 0.14 b	0.17 ± 0.11 b
LC ₅₀	1.49 ± 0.27 ab	0.78 ± 0.12 a	0.13 ± 0.03 a	0.07 ± 0.01 a
LC ₇₅	1.12 ± 0.33 a	0.72 ± 0.21 a	0.02 ± 0.003 a	0.02 ± 0.002 a

The results are Means±SD; Within the column similar alphabets are statistically not significant (p > 0.05 by DMRT). CR = Consumption Rate, GR = Growth Rate, RGR = Relative Growth Rate, RCR = Relative consumption Rate

The research results revealed that all concentrations of n-hexane, ethyl acetate, ether, and n-butanol of *P. methysticum* given were able to reduce the relative consumption rate (RCR) of the larvae tested. Such a reduction might be more significant as the concentration of extract given increased. The reduction of RCR of the larvae tested with n-hexane was equal to LC₁₅ – LC₇₅ with the percentage of 10.76%; 50.20%; 34.46%; and 36.65%, respectively. Meanwhile, the percentage of reduction in relative consumption rate (RCR) of larvae tested with ethyl acetate was equal to LC₁₅-LC₇₅ with 15.86%, 17.47%,31.18%, and 53.49%, respectively. The percentage of reduction in relative consumption rate (RCR) of larvae tested with diethyl ether from 349ppm concentration (LC₁₅) – 34.920 ppm (LC₇₅) was 2.72%; 4.55%; 4.55%; and 19.32%, respectively. The percentage of

reduction of larvae tested with n-butanol starting from 20 ppm concentration (LC_{15}) – 2.585 ppm (LC_{75}) was 24.22%; 32.81%; 39.06%; and 43.75%, respectively.

The higher the concentration was, the lower the consumption rate would be. Larvae would respond by reducing the consumption because the feed was contaminated with bioactive compound of high concentration. The decrease in relative consumption rate was possibly because of the existence of allelochemical compound in the feed consumed. Such a mechanism occurred because the existence of bioactive compound in extract *P. methyticum* served as antifeedant.

The reduction of the feed consumed by larvae was due to the existence of allelochemical compound content dissolved in n-hexane, ethyl acetate, diethyl ether, and n-butanol of *P. methyticum* as the feed for the insects. Slansky and Scriber (1985) agreed that larvae would reduce the amount of feed consumed whenever there was toxin in the feed. It was also asserted that the toxin would not take any effect at the first time the larvae started consuming the feed, but it might take some time for the body system to be affected so that the larvae would finally reduce the amount of feed ingested. It was because the insects attempt to reduce the amount of toxin coming into their body together with the feed.

The extract of n-hexane, ethyl acetate, diethyl ether, and n-butanol of *P. methyticum* is generally capable of reducing the relative growth rate (RGR) of the larvae. From the LC_{15} , it is seen that the RGR had shown significant influence when compared to control. The percentage of reduction in RGR of the larvae tested from the concentration LC_{15} - LC_{75} of each extract was 52.01-88.35%; 20.68-70.54%; 35.57-93.23%; and 31.27-94.00%, respectively. The percentage of reduction in RGR of the larvae tested with concentration LC_{15} - LC_{75} of n-hexane was as much as 52.73–89.09%; 20.55-71.23%; 37.50-93.75%; 32.00-92.00%, respectively.

The reduction of RCR affected the reduction of RGR. The decreasing RCR caused the feed intake, changed into biomass, to be lower. The weight of larvae was affected by the amount of feed consumed. The amount of feed consumed by larvae was affected by the quality of nutrition of the feed (Slansky and Scriber 1985). The existence of allelochemical compound, which was toxic, would influence the amount and rate of consumption, leading to the decreasing growth rate and final weight. When the feed consumed contained any toxic compound, the larvae would not be able to reach ideal weight that allowed them to turn into pupae (Simpson and Simpson, 1990). Slansky and Scriber (1985) believed that not all energy obtained from the feed consumed increased the weight of larvae. Some energy was used to detoxify any toxin that came with the feed. So, the weight of larvae was reduced. The quality and quantity of

feed consumed could influence the growth, development, and reproduction of insects (Scriber and Slansky, 1981). The reduced value of RCR and RGR showed that the toxin from allelochemical substance in the peritrophic membrane was effective, and it indicated that there was deterioration on the cellular surface of midgut (Marie et al., 2009). The distribution of four-type extract of *P. methycticum* also affected the values of ECD and ECI and AD of the tested larvae (Table 3).

Table 3. Effect of extract of *Piper methycticum* for Conversion Efficiency of digested food (ECD), Efficiency of Conversion of Ingested Food (ECI), as well as estimates of the Approximate Digestibility (AD) third instar larvae of *Plutella xylostella*

Crude Concentrate (ppm)	Ekstrak	ECD (%)	ECI (%)	AD (%)
n-Hexane				
0		28,38 ± 7,41 c	12,50 ± 3,80 c	45,99 ± 12,86 a
LC ₁₅		21,05 ± 6,91 b	12,26 ± 1,37 c	52,35 ± 6,28 ab
LC ₂₅		19,17 ± 8,02 b	10,70 ± 3,72 bc	57,70 ± 7,35 b
LC ₅₀		14,88 ± 4,21 ab	8,88 ± 1,75 ab	60,92 ± 8,67 b
LC ₇₅		9,26 ± 3,08 a	7,16 ± 2,33 a	78,18 ± 6,85 c
Ethyl acetate				
0		35,73 ± 6,680 d	20,25 ± 5,85 c	57,36 ± 14,62 a
LC ₁₅		27,92 ± 3,452 c	18,66 ± 2,63 b	66,72 ± 3,78 b
LC ₂₅		23,49 ± 2,986 bc	15,52 ± 1,99 ab	66,30 ± 5,26 b
LC ₅₀		18,33 ± 6,220 ab	14,78 ± 4,39 ab	71,63 ± 5,67 b
LC ₇₅		16,51 ± 4,794 a	12,95 ± 3,88 a	89,42 ± 1,14 c
Diethyl ether				
0		42,54 ± 13,39d	19,70 ± 5,85 e	46,82 ± 5,52 a
LC ₁₅		22,10 ± 6,02 b	14,32 ± 3,47 d	65,47 ± 6,67 b
LC ₂₅		13,92 ± 1,74 b	10,20 ± 1,39 c	73,21 ± 2,79 c
LC ₅₀		7,62 ± 2,38 ab	5,94 ± 1,47 b	79,27 ± 5,24 d
LC ₇₅		1,49 ± 0,26 a	1,24 ± 0,19 a	83,14 ± 2,67 d
n-Butanol				
0		46,38 ± 8,43 e	19,64 ± 6,04 c	42,61 ± 10,89 a
LC ₁₅		37,04 ± 8,45 d	20,31 ± 6,38 c	54,08 ± 7,31 b
LC ₂₅		23,79 ± 7,15 c	16,24 ± 5,61 c	67,47 ± 8,01 c
LC ₅₀		11,28 ± 1,17 b	8,45 ± 0,67 b	75,13 ± 2,43 c
LC ₇₅		2,53 ± 0,70 a	2,16 ± 0,55 a	83,20 ± 2,50 d

The results are Means±SD; Within the column similar alphabets are statistically not significant (p > 0.05 by DMRT).

The values of ECD and ECI of the tested larvae tended to fall as the concentration of extracts given increased (Table 3). The figures of reduction in ECD with the concentration equal to LC₁₅-LC₇₅ of n-hexane were 27.41;32.45;47.57; and 67.37%, and of ethyl acetate were 21.86; 34.26; 48.70; and 53.79%, of diethyl ether were 48.05;67.28;42.09; and 96.50%, and of n-butanol were 20.14; 48.71; 75.68; and 94.55%. The percentage of reduction in the value of

ECI of larvae tested with concentration equal to LC₁₅ – LC₇₅ of n-hexane extract was as much as 1.91; 14.40; 28.96; and 42.70%, of ethyl acetate was 7.85; 23.36; 27.01; and 36.05%, of diethyl ether was 27.31; 48.22; 69.85; and 93.71%, of n-butanol was 3.41; 17.67; 56.78; and 89.00%.

In order to balance the amount of feed consumed against the decrease in the value of ECD, the AD needs to be increased so that the growth of larvae are not influenced (Table 3). The increase in AD of larvae tested with the concentration of LC₁₅-LC₇₅ of n-hexane was as much as 13.85-70.00%, of ethyl acetate 16.30-55.88%, of diethyl ether 39.84-77-59%, and of n-butanol 26.91 - 95.23%.

Simpson and Simpson (1990a; 1990b) suggested that insects would not finish their eating, for the feed given was not varied, which leads to the influence given to the efficiency of feed digested (ECD) and ingested (ECI). The decrease in ECD was caused by the fact that insects reacted metabolically to detoxify the toxin from allelochemical compound in the feed consumed, so that it affected the growth rate of insects (Slansky and Scriber, 1985). The digestive rate was influenced by the dry weight of feed consumed and the dry weight of stool. The conversion efficiency of the digested food was affected by the increasing weight of the insects (Chapman, 1995; 1998).

The decrease in the values of RGR, ECI, and ECD could hamper the growth and development of larvae and the chance for the larvae to form pupae. As a result, the fecundity and life span of the larvae were affected; larvae may also be vulnerable to diseases (Khosravi *et al.*, 2010). The ECI and ECD caused the feed in the colon to be exposed to digestive enzyme for a long period, leading to the increase of AD. On the other hand, the need for energy was also urgent for the growth, development, movement, and detoxification; therefore, the insects would attempt to get the energy by increasing the AD (Slansky and Scriber, 1985).

The increase in AD could be detected by observing the stool excreted. It is assumed that the stool excreted consisted not only the indigestible food remnants, but also elements from peritrophic membrane which was crashed due to the allelochemical compound in the feed. Pyensor (1980) stated that alkaloid could cause irritation in alimentary canals by destroying the peritrophic membrane of the canals of larvae tested. The alkaloid compound is toxic to all vertebrate. It destroys the nervous systems and cellular membranes. Such a compound usually hampers acetylcholinesterase enzyme, so that such an enzyme may deposit in synapses and hamper any transmission in the nervous systems (Harbone, 1996; Rattan, 2010). Similarly, saponin compound is also able to reduce the activity of protease that takes place in alimentary canals of an

insect, influencing the intake process of nutrition; therefore, the unprocessed feed will be excreted in the form of stool (Gershenson and Croteau, 1991).

In other words, larvae instar IV *P. xylostella* gave response to allelochemical compound in the feed with *P. methyticum* extract to compensate. The response result could be seen in the decrease in RCR, together with the increase in the AD. The increase in AD was in line with what is suggested in Simpson and Simpson (1990) that larvae would increase their ability to digest feed (AD) when toxic chemical compound exists in their body.

CONCLUSIONS

The results of the research showed that the extract of Ethyl acetate of *P. methyticum* leaf is able to suppress anti-eating activity done by larvae *P. xylostella* instar III as much as 92.79%. It reduced relative consumption rate (RCR), relative growth rate, efficiency of conversion of digested food, efficiency of conversion of ingested food, and it increased average digested food. Extract of *P. methyticum* is potential to be developed as botanical insecticide to control pests *P. xylostella*.

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